

General Forms of Universal Connections of Elastic Fibrous Composites

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SUMMARY: We explore the universal connections between the overall moduli of elastic fibrous composites. For any medium that can be represented by certain characterization functions, we show that its effective modulus tensors follow similar constraints as those for Hill's connections for a two-phase fibrous composite. Some new standpoints are proposed, which reveal that the connections remain valid for media containing cavities or rigid inclusions. In addition, connections are devised to accommodate the case in which the composite consists of phases with identical eigen-moduli. We show that, in this particular case, it often provides additional constraints to the overall moduli of the composite.

KEYWORDS: effective moduli, universal connections, anisotropy, elastic fibrous composites.

INTRODUCTION

Sometimes in a heterogeneous medium certain local fields may be spatially uniform. For instance, in a cylindrical body a constant axial strain or electric field may be prescribed or induced. In addition, in thermo-elastostatics one may assume that a uniform temperature change prevails in a solid. Quite a few exact theorems of composites are indeed a consequence of the existence of such constant fields. For example, Hill [9] found that the overall elastic moduli of two-phase fibrous composites are connected by universal relations which are independent of the geometry at a given volume fraction. Levin [10] showed that the effective mechanical properties and thermal expansion coefficient are related in an exact manner. Rosen and Hashin [13] derived a relation between the specific heat and thermo-mechanical moduli. All these theorems are microstructure independent and provide theoretical linkages among the overall moduli of the composite. The results were originally presented in terms of isotropic or transversely isotropic elasticity, where explicit formulae can be found. In a series of works, Dvorak [4-5] showed that, in the presence of a certain constant field, it is possible to generate uniform fields throughout the medium by a particular set of loadings. With this concept, much progress has been made in finding the connections between the moduli of composites with arbitrary anisotropy or with other physical context, such as piezoelectricity (see for example, Benveniste and Dvorak, [6] and references cited therein). Recently, Chen [3] showed that, upon a rearrangement of moduli, all the aforementioned connections are mathematically equivalent to each other and can be treated in a unified manner. However the uniform field approach

is not without limitation and the applicability of the connections may not seem readily apparent from the existing presentations. In fact, there are quite a few theoretically interesting situations in which the uniform field method may exhibit difficulty or even break down, for instance in porous media or in composites with identical bulk or shear moduli. This work proposes some new standpoints to these issues and intends to provide a solution to resolve the gap. The formulation will focus exclusively on elastic cylindrical aggregates, which are sufficient to generate results in many different contexts, including thermal effects, humidity, electric fields, etc. We also presents a general framework for the subject, which is suitable for different physical contexts. Central to the concept is the existence of *certain* constant quantities, e.g. temperature, axial strain, etc.

UNIVERSAL CONNECTIONS

To illustrate the main concept of the framework, we shall focus on purely elastic behavior of fibrous composites. The concept will be sufficient to extend to other physical contexts, such as piezoelectricity, thermal effects, etc. On a fixed Cartesian coordinate system $\{x_i\}$, the constitutive equations for an elastic solid are given by $\sigma_{ij} = L_{ijkl}\epsilon_{kl}$ or $\epsilon_{ij} = S_{ijkl}\sigma_{kl}$. In matrix notation, they can be expressed as $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{L}\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ or $\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \mathbf{S}\boldsymbol{\sigma}$.

Suppose the axial direction is chosen as parallel to the x_3 axis. Then the usual Hooke's law can be rearranged as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} \\ -\sigma_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{S}} & \mathbf{a} \\ \mathbf{a}^T & -E_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \\ \epsilon_3^0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \\ \sigma_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{L}} & \mathbf{b} \\ \mathbf{b}^T & l_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} \\ \epsilon_3^0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} &= [\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_4, \sigma_5, \sigma_6]^T, & \hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} &= [\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \epsilon_4, \epsilon_5, \epsilon_6]^T, \\ \mathbf{a} &= [s_{13}, s_{23}, s_{34}, s_{35}, s_{36}]^T / s_{33}, & \mathbf{b} &= [l_{13}, l_{23}, l_{34}, l_{35}, l_{36}]^T, \\ (\hat{\mathbf{L}})_{ij} &= l_{ij}, & (\hat{\mathbf{S}})_{ij} &= s_{ij} - s_{i3}s_{j3}/s_{33}, \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 4, 5, 6), \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

E_3 is the Young's modulus in the x_3 direction, and s_{ij} and l_{ij} are the usual two-index compliance and stiffness, respectively. The superscript T denotes the matrix transpose. The field quantities must satisfy the equilibrium equations and compatibility conditions. Along any interfaces of different materials, perfect bonding is assumed.

Let us now consider a heterogeneous medium consisting of cylindrical phases with arbitrary transverse geometry. Suppose that the properties of the medium can be represented by the forms

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{S}}(x_1, x_2) &= \hat{\mathbf{S}}_\alpha + (\hat{\mathbf{S}}_\beta - \hat{\mathbf{S}}_\alpha)\mathbf{F}(x_1, x_2), \\ \mathbf{a}(x_1, x_2) &= \mathbf{a}_\alpha + \mathbf{F}^T(x_1, x_2)(\mathbf{a}_\beta - \mathbf{a}_\alpha), \\ E_3(x_1, x_2) &= E_3^\alpha + (E_3^\beta - E_3^\alpha)f(x_1, x_2), \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

in which $\{\hat{\mathbf{S}}_i, \mathbf{a}_i, E_3^i\}$, $i = \alpha, \beta$, are two sets of constant properties. $\mathbf{F}(x_1, x_2)$ and $f(x_1, x_2)$ are certain functions of position restricted by the requirements that the compliances be symmetric and nonnegative. The objective of this work is to show that the effective moduli of the considered medium will follow the universal connections as those for a two-phase fibrous composite.

Suppose, under a uniform loading, the macroscopic behavior of the medium can be effectively represented by the same constitutive relation (1) with certain suitably chosen overall moduli $\hat{\mathbf{S}}^*$, \mathbf{a}^* and E_3^* . Then the average fields satisfy

$$\begin{bmatrix} \langle \hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} \rangle \\ -\langle \sigma_3 \rangle \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{S}}^* & \mathbf{a}^* \\ \mathbf{a}^{*T} & -E_3^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \langle \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \rangle \\ \epsilon_3^0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where the argument inside $\langle \rangle$ means the volume averages over the representative volume element (RVE). By taking the average of (1) and comparing with (4) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta \hat{\mathbf{S}}^* \langle \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \rangle + \Delta \mathbf{a}^* \epsilon_3^0 &= \Delta \hat{\mathbf{S}} \langle \mathbf{F} \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \rangle + \langle \mathbf{F}^T \rangle \Delta \mathbf{a} \epsilon_3^0, \\ \Delta \mathbf{a}^{*T} \langle \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \rangle - \Delta E_3^* \epsilon_3^0 &= \Delta \mathbf{a}^T \langle \mathbf{F} \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \rangle - \Delta E_3 \langle f \rangle \epsilon_3^0,\end{aligned}\quad (5)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta \hat{\mathbf{S}}^* &= \hat{\mathbf{S}}^* - \hat{\mathbf{S}}_\alpha, & \Delta \mathbf{a}^* &= \mathbf{a}^* - \mathbf{a}_\alpha, & \Delta E_3^* &= E_3^* - E_3^\alpha, \\ \Delta \hat{\mathbf{S}} &= \hat{\mathbf{S}}_\beta - \hat{\mathbf{S}}_\alpha, & \Delta \mathbf{a} &= \mathbf{a}_\beta - \mathbf{a}_\alpha, & \Delta E_3 &= E_3^\beta - E_3^\alpha.\end{aligned}\quad (6)$$

Since $\langle \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \rangle$ and ϵ_3^0 can be prescribed arbitrarily, by letting $\epsilon_3^0 = 0$, relations (9) provide

$$\Delta \mathbf{a}^* = \Delta \hat{\mathbf{S}}^* \Delta \hat{\mathbf{S}}^{-1} \Delta \mathbf{a}, \quad (7)$$

while, letting $\langle \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \rangle = 0$, they lead to

$$-[\Delta E_3^* - \langle f \rangle \Delta E_3] = \Delta \mathbf{a}^T \Delta \hat{\mathbf{S}}^{-1} [\Delta \mathbf{a}^* - \langle \mathbf{F}^T \rangle \Delta \mathbf{a}]. \quad (8)$$

Equations (7,8) provide at most *six* constraints to the overall properties of the non-homogeneous medium, which means that the six material constants relevant to the axial direction of the cylindrical aggregate can be solely determined by the remaining 15 off-axial material constants. In particular, the connection (7) suggests that the overall moduli of *a family of* heterogeneous materials are governed by the same constraints as that for a typical two-phase fibrous composite. In addition, the relationship (7) is independent of volume concentrations of the constituents. The functions \mathbf{F} and f , which are relevant to the volume concentrations of the phases, only take effect in one connection (8).

For the usual two-phase composite, it follows that $\langle \mathbf{F} \rangle = c_2 \mathbf{I}$ and $\langle f \rangle = c_2$, where c_2 denotes the volume fraction of phase 2. Equations (7) and (8) are recast as

$$\begin{aligned}(\mathbf{a}^* - \mathbf{a}_1) &= (\hat{\mathbf{S}}^* - \hat{\mathbf{S}}_1)(\hat{\mathbf{S}}_2 - \hat{\mathbf{S}}_1)^{-1}(\mathbf{a}_2 - \mathbf{a}_1), \\ -(E_3^* - c_1 E_3^1 - c_2 E_3^2) &= (\mathbf{a}_2 - \mathbf{a}_1)^T (\hat{\mathbf{S}}_2 - \hat{\mathbf{S}}_1)^{-1} (\mathbf{a}^* - c_1 \mathbf{a}_1 - c_2 \mathbf{a}_2),\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

which are exactly the results of Chen ([3], Eqs.27₁, 28₁) derived from the uniform-field approach. The present formulation does not invoke the concept of uniform fields and yet the scope is somewhat broader than that of the previous works. For example, the present approach justifies the validity of the connections for media containing cavities or rigid inclusions, and for a few classes of pointwise varying materials, in which uniform fields may not be generated. We note, however, that for a general three- or more-phase material, no such connections (7,8) can be found by either approach. As noted earlier by Chen [3], the connections are formally identical with Levin's [10] relation, Rosen and Hashin's [13] connection between the effective thermal properties and overall mechanical properties, and with the restrictions of the overall electrical-mechanical coupling behavior, etc. Thus, by proper interpretations of the definitions in (7) and (8), the results also apply to the constraints of overall moduli of various physical phenomena.

GENERAL FRAMEWORK

In the previous section we focused on the constraints between the overall elastic moduli of fibrous composites, in which the axial strain ϵ_3 can be taken constant. In fact, as long as certain local fields are uniform throughout the medium, the framework remains valid. For example, in a cylindrical electro-elastic aggregate the axial strain and

axial electric field may be taken constant; also in a layered medium the strains in the transverse direction can be assumed uniform under certain loadings. Apart from these, uniform eigenfields, or transformation fields may be regarded as particular examples of this kind. In this section, we propose a general framework for deriving the connections between the overall moduli of two-phase composites. The formulation is not limited to the context of elasticity. For general purposes, let us characterize the physical behavior for the phases (designated as 1 and 2) as

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{U}_i = \mathbf{P}_i \mathbf{X}_i + \mathbf{Q}_i \mathbf{Y}_i, \\ \mathbf{V}_i = \mathbf{Q}_i^T \mathbf{X}_i + \mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{Y}_i, \end{cases} \quad : i = 1, 2, \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{P}^T$ and $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{R}^T$, \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{X} are $(n - r) \times 1$ matrices, and \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{Y} are $r \times 1$ matrices. Suppose \mathbf{Y} represents the uniform local field quantities throughout the medium, i.e. $\mathbf{Y}_1 = \mathbf{Y}_2 = \mathbf{Y}^u = \text{constant matrix}$, which means that there exist r uniform fields among the n field quantities.

If, in addition, the local variables fulfill certain field equations (for instance, equilibrium equations in elasticity or divergence equation in dielectric problem) so that the average fields over the representative volume Ω are equal to the remote applied loading, namely $\bar{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{X}^\infty$ and $\bar{\mathbf{Y}} = \mathbf{Y}^u$, then the overall moduli are necessarily connected by relations of type

$$\begin{cases} \bar{\mathbf{U}} = \mathbf{P}^* \mathbf{X}^\infty + \mathbf{Q}^* \mathbf{Y}^u, \\ \bar{\mathbf{V}} = \mathbf{Q}^{*T} \mathbf{X}^\infty + \mathbf{R}^* \mathbf{Y}^u, \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where

$$\bar{\mathbf{M}} = \frac{1}{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{M} d\Omega, \quad \mathbf{M} = \mathbf{U}, \mathbf{V}, \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}. \quad (12)$$

Now taking average of the field variables and comparing with (11), in analogy to (5), one finds

$$\begin{cases} \Delta \mathbf{P}^* \mathbf{X}^\infty + \Delta \mathbf{Q}^* \mathbf{Y}^u = c \{ \Delta \mathbf{P} \langle \mathbf{X} \rangle + \Delta \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{Y}^u \}, \\ \Delta \mathbf{Q}^{*T} \mathbf{X}^\infty + \Delta \mathbf{R}^* \mathbf{Y}^u = c \{ \Delta \mathbf{Q} \langle \mathbf{X} \rangle + \Delta \mathbf{R} \mathbf{Y}^u \}, \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \mathbf{P}^* &= \mathbf{P}^* - \mathbf{P}_1, \quad \Delta \mathbf{Q}^* = \mathbf{Q}^* - \mathbf{Q}_1, \quad \Delta \mathbf{R}^* = \mathbf{R}^* - \mathbf{R}_1, \\ \Delta \mathbf{P} &= \mathbf{P}_2 - \mathbf{P}_1, \quad \Delta \mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{Q}_2 - \mathbf{Q}_1, \quad \Delta \mathbf{R} = \mathbf{R}_2 - \mathbf{R}_1, \\ c &= \Omega_2 / \Omega, \quad \Omega = \Omega_1 + \Omega_2, \quad \langle \mathbf{X} \rangle = \frac{1}{\Omega} \int_{\Omega_2} \mathbf{X} d\Omega. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Since \mathbf{X}^∞ and \mathbf{Y}^u can be prescribed arbitrarily, by letting $\mathbf{Y}^u = 0$ or $\mathbf{X}^\infty = 0$ separately, we find the connections between the overall moduli

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \mathbf{Q}^* &= \Delta \mathbf{P}^* (\Delta \mathbf{P})^{-1} \Delta \mathbf{Q}, \\ \Delta \mathbf{R}^* - c \Delta \mathbf{R} &= \Delta \mathbf{Q}^T (\Delta \mathbf{P})^{-1} [\Delta \mathbf{P}^* - c \Delta \mathbf{P}] (\Delta \mathbf{P})^{-1} \Delta \mathbf{Q}, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

provided that $\Delta \mathbf{P}$ is invertible.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

For a cylindrical body in which the material properties can be represented by the characterization formulae (3), we show that its effective moduli follow the constraints similar to those for two-phase fibrous media [9]. In fact, it can be shown that (3) is the most general characterization for which such connections can be established. Equation (3) permits us to characterize a domain that is more general than a two- or multi-phase medium or even a pointwise varying material, but in principle they cannot depict a general

three-phase material. However, for a three-phase material in which the third phase is itself a composite of the first two materials, or the family of three-phase materials that could be characterized by (4), then the results (7,8) still hold. The connections provide relationships between the moduli in the axial direction and those relating to the off-axial direction. In general at most six conditions can be obtained and thus only 15 out of a total of 21 constants are independent. Finally, we remark that, in addition to the various physical contexts mentioned in section 5, the present framework can be applied to polycrystals (see, for example, [2,14]).

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